

MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLEX RECTAL FISTULAS

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Introduction. Today, if we talk not about a single universal method, but about the development of a certain direction, approach to the treatment of rectal fistula, there are significant positive changes [1, 2, 4, 6]. Thus, since the end of the last century, against the background of the development of medical technology began to appear and actively develop methods of treatment of rectal fistula, in which the sphincter apparatus is not directly affected [3, 5, 7].

Purpose of the study is to improve the results of treatment of rectal fistula patients by improving the technical aspects of fistula excision.

Materials and methods. The study is based on the data of examination and treatment of patients with rectal fistula operated in the proctology department of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University in the period from 2018 to 2023. 134 cases were selected for the prospective dynamic active study. Among them were patients with transsphincteric and extrasphincteric rectal fistulas. All patients were operated on routinely and, depending on the chosen treatment tactics, were divided into two groups. The first group, the Control group, included 56 (41.0%) patients who underwent fistula excision using traditional methods. The second group, the main group, included 78 (59.0%) patients in whom fistula dissection was performed using modified instruments. In the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University, when performing excision of rectal fistulas until 2020, we used exclusively traditional methods, after which there were well-known disadvantages - insufficiency and stricture of the anal sphincter, recurrence of rectal fistula, etc. These circumstances prompted us to search for more gentle, less traumatic and at the same time radical methods of surgery. As a result, since 2021, the choice of surgical treatment for rectal fistulas has been differentiated taking into account the individual peculiarities for each patient. When choosing the method of surgical treatment we were guided by the results of preoperative diagnostics. MRI was combined with ultrasound and fistulography data. We took into account the gender of the patients, as well as the location and degree of complexity of the fistulous passage.

When performing LIFT (Ligation of Intersphincteric Fistula Tract) surgery, i.e. ligation of the fistulous passage in the intersphincteric space and removal of the proximal part of the fistula from the rectum, in addition to the standard set of surgical instruments, we additionally used a dissector and a modified button probe with an olive, which we developed. The dissector was necessary to isolate the part of the fistulous passage located in the intersphincteric space, especially the “posterior” part, which is the most proximal to the fistula surface and is not visualized from the wound side. The end of the dissector was inserted behind the fistulous canal and bypassed and reintroduced into the wound. Subsequently, the instrument was needed to grasp the ends of threads, which were brought under the highlighted segment of the fistula and used to ligate the passage along its length. A modified button-shaped probe with an olive was necessary to introduce the probe into the lumen of the fistulous passage from the side of the internal opening and the fistulous passage was tied with ligature at the level of the rod notch. When pulling the probe backward, the olive fixes the fistula mucosa and pulls it into the lumen of the rectum, i.e. the proximal part of the fistulous passage swells into the lumen of the rectum on the inside, the fistula is cut off at the very base after stitching and ligation. As we all know, in tortuous fistulous tracts, conventional grooved or button-shaped probes do not pass through the fistulous tract to the internal opening of the fistula, therefore, in addition to the standard set of instruments, we used a flexible cylindrical conductor developed by us, which easily penetrated through complex tortuous, branched fistulous tracts when inserted through the external or internal opening. This subgroup included 49 patients. The average age of patients in this group was 45.3 ± 7.1 years. Depending on the degree of complexity of the fistulous passage, the following operations were performed in the main group of patients with extrasphincteric fistulas: excision of extrasphincteric fistula of the I-II degree of complexity without damage to the muscle fibers of the anal ileum using a modified guide, and excision of extrasphincteric fistula of the III-IV degree of complexity with opening of the purulent cavity. This subgroup included 29 patients. The mean age of the patients in this subgroup was 52.1 ± 9.7 years.

Results. In order to examine the immediate results, pain intensity was assessed using a linear visual analog scale. Pain intensity was assessed at rest on days 1, 3, and 5 and after 1, 2, and 3 acts of defecation. The patient was asked to indicate on the line the level of pain he/she felt at the moment. The distance from the left border of the line (point “no pain”) to the point marked by the

patient was then measured in centimeters, rounding the value obtained. Each centimeter corresponds to one point of pain intensity. In the main group of patients who underwent LIFT surgery without anal sphincter disruption using a modified button probe or a flexible cylindrical conductor with olive, the average intensity of pain sensations at rest on the first day after surgery was 6.0 ± 0.2 points. By the 5th day after surgery the pain intensity decreased 3.8 times, reaching the level of 1.6 ± 0.3 points ("very mild pain"). In the Control group of patients who used the ligature method, there were severe pain sensations at rest on the first day after surgery, reaching the level of 7.8 ± 0.4 points. However, by the 5th day after surgery, the intensity of pain decreased to 4.3 ± 0.2 points ("medium pain"). The majority of patients in the studied groups (64.2%) experienced the first act of defecation 3 days after surgery. In the main group after the first act of defecation, the average intensity of pain sensations was 3.6 ± 0.2 points, which is described as "weak pain" sensations. In the Control group after the first act of defecation, the intensity of pain sensations after the first act of defecation was 5.5 ± 0.4 points, which corresponds to the level of "medium pain". In the main group after the third act of defecation the intensity of pain sensations sharply decreased to 1.1 ± 0.3 points, which is characterized as "very weak pain", and in half of the cases there was a complete absence of pain sensations. In the Control group, after the third act of defecation, pain sensations of "medium degree" were noted, assessed as 3.8 ± 0.2 points. Thus, patients who underwent LIFT surgery with the use of modified guides and without disruption of the muscle fibers of the anal groin have a significant reduction in the level of pain syndrome in the postoperative period and after acts of defecation. This reduction in pain reduces the need for narcotic analgesics and significantly improves the quality of life of patients. During the first two days after surgery, the patients of the main group were changed daily aseptic dressings in the perianal area, after which daily dressings were no longer required. This reduced the workload of the medical staff and decreased the consumption of dressings. In the Control group, daily dressings were performed with periodic tightening of the ligature every 4-5 days until its removal. In the Control group, 4 patients (7.1%) had abscessation of the fistulous passage. We associate this complication with incomplete removal of the distal part of the fistulous passage, which led to the subsequent development of abscess. The patients underwent abscess opening on the 2-3 day after the operation. After that they were discharged from the hospital on the 5th-6th day after abscess opening in satisfactory condition.

Conclusion. The developed innovations in the technical aspects of surgical treatment of patients with rectal fistulas led to an improvement in the standards of medical care, reducing the incidence of immediate postoperative complications from 8.9% to 2.6%. The use of a modified button probe and flexible cylindrical conductor with olive in the surgical treatment of complex rectal fistulae not only simplifies the process of technical implementation, but also prevents damage to the muscle fibers of the anal ileum.

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